

**PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF FAMILY INSTITUTE
DEVELOPMENT****Ramazonov Jahangir Djalolovich**

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Abstract: The article talks about the essence of family and family relations, marital relations, the role of the neighborhood in family relations, economic, legal, psychological and spiritual relations, the school of family education, the environment and the importance of adaptation to new conditions.

Key words: marriage, social role, social status, society, interpersonal relations, family environment.

The family plays a primary role in the education of a person compared to other social institutions. Because it is in the family that individual abilities, personal and professional interests, and moral norms are formed. The family factor affects a person throughout his life. From a social point of view, the family is a community in which a person occupies various social roles. Family helps a person to define himself and increase his social and creative activity. In our republic, where family relations are considered the highest value, the social status of the family in Uzbekistan is extremely high and it maintains its status until now. However, the family crisis in this situation affects many families, including Uzbek families. In Uzbek families with many children, the preservation of the patriarchal order ensured the stability of family relations, because the necessary educational factor and skills in the Uzbek family are passed from generation to generation. Due to the decrease in the number of family members and the increasing problem of the separation of generations, the issue of forming family relations is becoming more and more important. Today, the family desperately needs the help of highly qualified psychologists, social pedagogues, and social workers.

The family exists in two directions: as a small social group and as a social institution. In the first case, it is a community formed on the basis of kinship and united by living together. In the second, it is a social institution in which the daily life of people takes place.

The neighborhood and the family stand out as social institutions that have been formed in the Uzbek nation since time immemorial, occupy a deep place in our lives, and are recognized at

the level of high values. The family, which unites people, is the main link of society, and the stability of the spiritual environment, the formation of a system of healthy relationships, and the well-being of the community, which is considered to be the eastern form of self-management of citizens, contribute to the development, present and future of the entire society. determines tomorrow.

In recent years, the strengthening of neighborhood and family institutions, increasing their social influence, and their comprehensive support have been considered as one of the priorities of state policy in our country, and systematic reforms are being implemented in this area. As a result, relevant regulatory legal documents have been adopted and are being put into practice. Family is a small group of people based on marriage or blood kinship ties, common way of life, moral responsibility and mutual support. The concepts of "Society" and "Family" are closely related to each other. This connection is seen in the fact that society cannot exist without families, and in turn, the family is formed and survives in a certain society. For example: in V. Karimova's book, "Even in the preservation of human society, the family plays the role of a special "buffer" - a bridge between some individual and the whole society. After all, educational institutions and centers of culture in the state and society have a certain role in preserving cultural and spiritual values and passing them on from generation to generation. The role of the family in preserving values cannot be higher." Social relations between the family and the society have a two-way relationship. Each family operates on the basis of the demands of the community. The development of the society is directly related to the level of formation of the social, economic and spiritual image of the families in its bosom. For example, if the demands of the social entity on families do not conflict with their interests, on the contrary, if they help to ensure the well-being and peace of families, then the indicator of the support and strengthening of social demands by families, ensuring their actual implementation is high. will be One of the scholars interested in the history of marriage was the ancient Greek philosopher Plato. In his opinion, the patriarchal family is the basis of social relations and community life in all times and places, and the state was formed from the union of such families. Taking care of people, their work, life and spiritual development is the main goal of our government. A person's qualities, his attitude to work, spiritual, ideological and cultural wealth are formed in the family. Mahalla today is not only an institution that expresses the solidarity and cooperation of families, their demands, needs, and interests, but on the contrary, it implements state policies in practice, carries out important political-social, cultural-educational activities to bring them to every family, and - is also a link that implements self-government and connects families with political and non-

political institutions in society. A neighborhood is a place that functions as a healthy social environment. For this reason, our government considers helping the population to improve their living conditions, connecting the neighborhood to the family, as a matter of state power. Vasila Karimova's works on the socio-psychological factors and consequences of family and family relations focus on the problems of preparing young people for gender relations in the family, the role of gender concepts in personal education (2006). The impact of marital and sibling relationships in the family on the child's personality, including the role in the formation of masculinity and femininity, has been studied and scientific conclusions have been drawn.

Family is a social unit based on natural, economic, legal and spiritual relations of people. Depending on its social content, the family usually consists of three interconnected social groups, marriage as its foundation, marital relations as the result of marriage, and children as the consequence of marital relations. Family is a school of education, the first stage of education. Parents are the first example for a child in a family, a teacher. The knowledge and life experiences that parents give to their children are a continuation of the knowledge and life experiences they have acquired from their parents. Relations between parents and children, knowledge and experiences given to young people are of great importance for their socialization. The formation of a child born in a family as a mature person is closely related to the education and upbringing of the family, the formation of the child's self-esteem, that is, the fulfillment of the family's social duties. In turn, the increase in the number of children in the family also affects the performance of the family's economic tasks. In other words, the increase in the number of family members living in the family requires the improvement of the family's material condition, that is, the improvement of the level of the family's economic tasks. Or let's take the social function of the family. The education provided in the family does not fail to influence the formation of the child's worldview, his relationship to society, people, and changes. As a child grows up in a family environment, his behavior, his attitude to the environment, his family, his thoughts about building a family and having children in the future are formed. If the social function of the family is fulfilled positively, that is, if the child develops feelings of respect for the family, parents, elders, and mutual help, then when he starts a family in the future, he will try to raise his children in the same way. Young people learn from their parents how to run a family business, provide for the family economically, and other experiences. Husband-wife relationship in young families is considered to be the most delicate and decisive form of relationship, which has its own regional, ethnic, sexual, age and individual psychological characteristics. According to psychologists and sociologists, brides and grooms whose age at first glance is not more than

30 are a young family. Usually, the concept of a young family includes the first 10 years of family life. After getting married and starting a family, it goes through several stages. Of these, the most observed and the most important from the social and psychological point of view is the stage of the young family.

At this stage, couples' ideas about family life are formed, children are born, and the main tasks related to their education and upbringing are carried out. Taking this into account, our government is carrying out a number of activities to ensure the stability of young families and their socio-economic and spiritual support, and to create opportunities to ensure the stability of the new family. Family life will have its own unevenness, ups and downs, complications and problems. One of such complications is the transition of a young couple to a new social status, position: husband, son-in-law, married, married, young man; related to the process of adaptation to the roles of wife, daughter-in-law, married woman, to a new social environment for them, to a new family. So, how does the process of adapting to these new conditions go? Of course, this process is easier for men than for women. Because, based on the ethnic characteristics of the Uzbek family, in most cases they live in their own house, with their parents and other relatives. remains in the system of family and interpersonal relations. The situation of a woman after marriage is drastically different from before. First, he gets into an environment that is almost new to him, somewhat different from his previous one. She moves from her childhood family, which has its own system of interpersonal relations and roles, to another family, a special family environment. Some of its features may not be compatible with the previous one. There is a great possibility of a difference in the requirements for this or that job. Moreover, the tasks assigned to a young bride in a young family may differ in terms of quantity and content from the tasks she performs during her childhood. One of the main reasons why the process of adapting to the new social conditions is difficult for a woman in Uzbek families is that the bride feels like a "stranger" in the new family, that is, "foreignness" is the existence of the effect. Thus, in some young people who started a family with the best intentions, the personal relationship of the couple begins to develop from good to bad against happiness, because the uplifting emotional closeness between the couple observed at the beginning of the marriage gradually decreases, and they become saturated in their feelings. happens. These situations certainly constitute a unique dynamic of the development of interpersonal relations in any family. Being aware of this situation and being ready for its changes is the basis for preventing some disappointments that may arise in young families.

In short, in order to ensure the stability of neighborhood and family institutions, the

implementation of the idea of "Prosperous family - prosperous neighborhood - prosperous society" should be implemented, systematic development of these institutions and further improvement of the legal framework in this regard, preservation and development of family values in society, neighborhood and expanding the scope of scientific-practical research and effective methodical-consultative support to families on issues of development of family institutions is becoming more urgent. This means that all employees working in the neighborhood and family system, in particular, the team of the "Neighborhood and Family" scientific-research institute, set themselves the task of finding innovative, scientific and practical solutions to existing problems related to the strengthening of these institutions. To solve these tasks, to further strengthen neighborhood and family institutions, to carry out effective activities in cooperation will undoubtedly serve the great goal of building a prosperous society.

Literature

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси. 24.01.2020 йил. (<https://uza.uz/uz/posts/zbekiston-respublikasiprezidenti-shavkat-mirziyeevning-oliy-25-01-2020>)4.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси. 29.12.2020 йил. (<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>)
3. "Маҳалла тизими ходимлари кунини белгилаш тўғрисида"ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонуни. 2020 йил 2 март. ЎРҚ-606-сон (<https://lex.uz/docs/-4751676>)
4. "Маҳалла ифтихори" кўкрак нишонини таъсис этиш тўғрисида"ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг ПҚ-3132-сон қарори. 2017 йил 13 июль. (<https://lex.uz/docs/3266714>)
5. Munavvarov A.K. Oila pedagogikasi. T., O'qituvchi. 1994.
6. Quronov M.Q. Qurboniyazova Z.Q. Ijtimoiy pedagogika. T., 2003.
7. Egamberdiyeva N. Ijtimoiy pedagogika. T., Alisher Navoiy nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy kutubxonasi. 2009.
8. Toxtaxodjayeva M.X va boshqalar. Pedagogika. T., O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati. 2010.
9. "Экономика и социум" №12(91) 2021 www.iupr.ru
10. Ismoilova N, Abdullayeva D. Ijtimoiy psixologiya. T., O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati. 2013.
11. Djalolovich, R. J. (2023). NIKOH-OILA MUNOSABATLARI SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI

TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(3), 473-477.

12. Ramazonov, J., & Xomidov, M. (2024). MILLIY QADRIYATLAR ASOSIDA SHAXS MA'NAVIY KAMOLOTI SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 3(1), 200-202.

13. Ramazonov, J. (2022). SHAXS DA REFLEKSIYA DARAJALARINING 'USIB BORI SH DINAMIKASINING IJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 10(10).

14. Ramazonov, J. (2021). Reflexive Mechanism-As The Main Form Of Controlling Students' Psychological Conditions. Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz), 7(7).

15. Ramazonov, J. (2022). SELF-ADMINISTRATION AS A SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 9(9).

16. Рамазонов, Ж. Ж. (2020). ОИЛАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАР ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯЛАШУВИНИНГ ИJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 594-596).